

Aerodynamic Lift in Low-Earth-Orbit Satellites: The Flat Plate Wing (Preprint)

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Abstract

In low-earth-orbit (LEO) a deviated airstream produces lift and a tilted flat plate makes it happen. A flat rectangular plate becomes a winged satellite in low-earth-orbit (LEO) with wingspan and chord length, and with angle of attack to climb, fly level, or descend. In LEO, above 150km, the flat plate shields its own top surface from the incident air stream for angles of attack roughly $> 10^\circ$, offering a drag-free zone for avionics and other devices. The air stream particles, mostly atomic oxygen AO and molecular nitrogen N_2 , impact the satellite surfaces with incident momentum p_i and reflect with outgoing momentum p_o , both quantities measured in ground-based laboratories. This work derives an analytical expression for the lift-to-drag ratio L/D of a rectangular plate, a function that depends on the outgoing momentum transfer ratio $f_o = p_o/p_i$ and the deflection δ of the outgoing particle. Laboratory data on atom-surface scattering applied to the L/D function show $L/D \approx 4$ to 1.6, depending on the surface, at small angles of attack (5 to 10°) decreasing to 0.5 at 50° , being 1.0 around 30° . The wing climbs when $L/D > 1.0$, flies level when $L/D = 1.0$ and descends when $L/D < 1.0$. Satellites in low-earth-orbit (LEO) lose their momentum to air particles in high velocity impacts that one-by-one remove momentum to produce drag. Between 150 and 200km drag severely limits orbit lifetime to less than one day and requires propulsion. Internet satellites fly at about 600 km where orbit lifetime is measured in years. Flight below 300km is desired in many applications to reduce communication power more than tenfold and the flat plate wing offers a feasible alternative that achieves maneuverable flight without propulsion - offering the possibility of active maneuvers for satellite collision avoidance. Surface erosion by AO is a serious problem in VLEO, but metallic surfaces erode far more slowly than polyimide Kapton and other space qualified polymers and are likely last several years at 200km.

Plain language summary

A flat plate wing offers a satellite that climbs, flies level, and descends without propulsion controlled by the angle between the plate and the satellite velocity (the angle of attack). At present, a satellite orbiting at 200km altitude re-enters within a day, but one at 600km where the density is roughly 1,000 times lower will not re-enter for several years; below 180km the satellite rapidly descends to incinerate on its way down. The satellite slows down, losing momentum in collisions with air molecules at a rate that depends on the number of molecules encountered per second and is thus proportional to the air density - for a satellite of area 1×1 meter² at 200km this rate is about 10^{19} collisions/second (1 followed by 19 zeroes collisions per second). The momentum carried off in each collision is small, but the high collision rate makes the net force sufficient to bring the satellite down in a few orbits from the 200km altitude.

In some collisions the molecules bounce off sideways away from the satellite direction, that is, the airstream impacting the satellite deviates from its original direction. For these collisions, the satellite loses less momentum but is kicked sideways by the momentum reflected perpendicular to the original direction -

in a familiar example a sharp nosecone used in hypersonic aircraft has very little drag because of the momentum deflected sideways.

This paper shows how a flat plate, simpler than a nosecone, can use the sideways momentum to provide lift and, with its favorable geometry, control its angle of attack to climb, fly level, and descend as desired; in addition it shields flight equipment mounted on the top of the wing from the incident airstream. The flat plate shape allows a simple formula for the change of lift-to-drag ratio L/D with angle of attack. The L/D formula is easily evaluated using laboratory data of atomic oxygen AO surface scattering and further supported by older data to extend L/D to very small angles of attack. When L/D exceeds 1.0 the extra lift makes the satellite climb, when less than 1.0 it descends, and when $L/D = 1.0$ lift cancels drag for level flight - in all three cases the satellite continuously falls toward the center of earth, its high velocity keeping it in orbit.

1 Introduction

This paper shows that it is possible to design a satellite that flies without propulsion in low earth orbits (LEO) above 150 km. It contains a short review of drag at the beginning of the space age, a description of satellite energetics, the momentum transfer approach to drag coefficients with examples leading to asymmetric flight for lift, and lift-to-drag ratios based on laboratory data on surface scattering, closing with a discussion of challenges and applications.

Early in the space age, the late 1950's, observations of satellite orbit decay due to atmospheric drag were used to obtain air density of the upper atmosphere above 200 km.[1, 2, 3]. Subsequent studies of the upper atmosphere revealed its composition, number densities, and energetics as manifested by neutral winds and temperatures, the principal constituents above 200 km being atomic oxygen AO and molecular nitrogen N_2 [4]. Those data motivated studies of atom-surface interactions to obtain the momentum transfer responsible for the drag force; free-molecule flow notions were already established, and orbit decay was further quantified with drag coefficients predicted in terms of free-molecular flow theory[5].

Drag in LEO is large because satellite velocities are high, about 8km/s, roughly $10\times$ the average random thermal speeds of the AO atoms and N_2 molecules encountered by the satellite - the 8km/s velocity corresponding to about 5 eV for AO and 9 eV for N_2 . Drag occurs with the particles taking momentum away from the satellite as they scatter from its surfaces, reflecting at angles and with kinetic energies that depend on the type of surface and its orientation with respect to the line of impact of the air particles. Thus, computation of drag forces may be a complex calculation that depends on satellite shape and complicated further if different materials face the incident particle flux.

The constant flux of air particles at these energies is difficult to reproduce in the laboratory, denying the ability to predict the state of a surface in orbit - the problem being that laboratory reproduction requires a surface bombarded in a vacuum chamber by 5eV AO and 9eV N_2 - energies equivalent to more than 50,000°Kelvin. In laboratory experiments, layers of adsorbed molecules cover the surfaces, adsorption energies being much less than a few eV - the same surface in orbit would be wiped clean by the 5 and 9 eV incident energies of AO and N_2 . Nonetheless, as long as only single particle impacts are important in satellite flight as they are above 150km, laboratory data using AO and N_2 beams in the range of, say, 2 to 12 eV kinetic energies are expected to provide reasonable estimates of drag coefficients and other effects of atom-surface interactions[12].

Early estimates of drag coefficients were guided by computations invoking diffuse and specular reflections, and several theoretical models were developed to take into account different combinations of diffuse and specular reflections[6]. For the earliest drag density determinations, Harris and Jastrow[1] used the drag coefficient for the sphere of $C_D = 2.3 \pm 0.3$. Those determinations were significant for upper atmosphere research above 200 km since they showed that previous density models were in error by at least one order

of magnitude. Other estimates of C_D for the sphere claimed that its uncertainty was significantly smaller than 15% [7], yet noted the lack of necessary data on gas-surface interactions. Much of the theoretical work done in the 1960's led to the conclusion that for the sphere C_D could never be less than 2.0.

Laboratory data for some commonly used satellite surfaces are not consistent with the simple picture of diffuse and specular reflections and evidence for specular scattering began to accumulate. The findings of Saltsburg and Smith[23] and Hays et al.[24] that the surface scattering is strongly specular at high velocities are consistent with later observations[12, 17].

At the kinetic energies of AO and N₂ (5 to 10 eV) in LEO, the resonant scattering that would account for particle trapping (adsorption) is not as probable as it is at lower energies in the range of phonon excitation[21]. For the same reason the use of accommodation coefficients of momentum and energy that require thermalization of incident particles with the surface impacted may not be as relevant to satellite drag estimates as originally thought - a review of the basic physics considerations in the molecule and atom interactions with surfaces can be found in ref [12].

Laboratory measurements of single particle encounters of AO and N₂, such as those recently reported by Xu et al.[17] and Jorge et al.[16] for AO and previously for N₂ in [12], are perhaps most likely to yield reliable drag coefficient estimates since single particle impacts are the sole source of drag above 150 km where AO and N₂ densities are low enough that their mean free paths λ exceed satellite dimensions, e.g., diameter D of a short cylindrical satellite - that is, the Knudsen number $K_n = D/\lambda \gg 1.0$. At altitudes below 150km the reflected particles may collide with incident particles a distance a few λ 's and bounce back towards the satellite; the number of those impacts increasing further down until a shroud forms around the satellite with additional complications that modify drag before surface heating becomes consequential at lower altitudes below 120km.

2 Energetics of Circular Orbits

Only circular orbits are considered here, but the results being local at the position of the satellite, they should be applicable to elliptical orbits as well. A satellite is put into circular orbit at the desired altitude h above earth's surface with energy from rocket engines; its distance from earth's center being $r = R_{\oplus} + h$, radius of the earth R_{\oplus} being constant. Therefore, the satellite vertical velocity $\dot{h} = \dot{r}$.

Given the gravitational constant G , the satellite's total energy E is negative, depending only on r and given by

$$E = -GmM_{\oplus}/2r, \quad (1)$$

where $E = K + P$ (kinetic energy $K = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$, potential energy $P = -GmM_{\oplus}/r$). Since the centripetal force that keeps the satellite in circular orbit is $mv^2/r = GM_{\oplus}m/r^2$, $K = GmM_{\oplus}/2r$ and eq.1 follows.

Once in orbit, the satellite loses energy from collisions with air molecules as it rams its way through the air with ram velocity V ; each impact with air particles of mass m transferring a fraction C of particle momentum $p = mV$ from the satellite to the particle; the fraction factor C depending on satellite surface properties and shape. The drag force is $F_D = dN/dt \times C \times p$ where $dN/dt = n \times V \times A_r$ is the number of impacts per unit time with satellite reference area A_r , $C \times p$ being the momentum transferred per impact; A_r the area projected along velocity V . With number density $n[\#/m^3]$, the mass density in kg/m³ is $\rho = \bar{m} \times n$ with \bar{m} the average molecular mass in kilograms.

Thus the drag force, given by

$$F_D = \frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 C_D A_r, \quad (2)$$

serves to define the drag coefficient as $C_D = 2C$ that incorporates the particular surface properties, including shape and materials, of the satellite. $C_D \simeq 2$ most often and is discussed in more detail in the next section.

An applied force F_a on the satellite may change its altitude h and thereby its total energy E by doing work at the rate $dE/dt = F_a \times V$. The drag force F_D is such a force as is propulsion (thrust). Drag opposes V to dissipate energy making $dE/dt < 0$ making the satellite descend with $\dot{h} < 0$ while propulsion makes $dE/dt > 0$ to climb with $\dot{h} > 0$; if propulsion matches drag then altitude is preserved in level flight with $\dot{h} = 0$.

Explicitly, since E depends only on r , eq.1 gives

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(-\frac{GmM_{\oplus}}{2r} \right) = \frac{GmM_{\oplus}}{2r^2} \dot{r} = F_a \times V, \quad (3)$$

and because $\dot{r} = \dot{h}$, eq.3 gives the rate of change of height h

$$\dot{h} = \frac{F_a \times V}{G(r)}, \quad (4)$$

where $G(r) = GmM_{\oplus}/2r^2$. If $F_a = F_D$, a 10kg satellite with area $A_r = 1\text{m}^2$ and $C_D \simeq 2.2$ loses altitude at the rate \dot{h} of about 4m/s, losing about 20 km in one orbit starting at 200km where air density $\rho \simeq 4 \times 10^{-10}\text{kg/m}^3$; drag dissipating about 200 Watts and thus requiring about 200 Watts of propulsion to maintain level flight at 200km. As the satellite descends, its velocity increases as $1/\sqrt{r}$ in accordance with Kepler's 3rd law with its orbital period proportional to r^3 .

This paper shows that just as drag makes $\dot{h} < 0$, it is possible to have an applied force due entirely to the air particle flux nV that results in a displacement perpendicular to V that, with proper orientation, makes $\dot{h} > 0$. We find that a lift force F_L is due to impacts with air particles in a satellite shaped to deflect particles away from V with a non-zero component perpendicular to V . It is thus possible to define a lift coefficient C_L with

$$F_L = \frac{1}{2}\rho V^2 C_L A, \quad (5)$$

and have

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = F_L V = \frac{1}{2}\rho V^3 C_L A > 0, \quad (6)$$

while E remains negative because the satellite's motion is bound with $E = -GmM_{\oplus}/2r < 0$.

For either F_D (eq. 2) or F_L (eq. 5) at 200km with $\rho \simeq 2 \times 10^{-10}\text{kg/m}^3$, equation 4 gives

$$\dot{h} \approx 16 \frac{AC}{m} \text{ [m/s]}, \quad (7)$$

where, given G, M_{\oplus} and $r = R_{\oplus} + h$, the satellite area A is in meters, its mass m in kg, and C is either $C_D \simeq 2.2$ or $C_L \simeq 1.0$.

With this relation, a likely satellite of mass $m = 50\text{kg}$ with area 1m^2 and no special design to enable lift would fall at the rate $\dot{h} \approx -0.7\text{m/s}$, losing about 4km in the orbit beginning at $h = 200\text{km}$, losing increasingly more as the density increases with loss of altitude.

On the other hand, a satellite like the one described below will likely have $A = 10\text{m}^2$ and $m = 50\text{kg}$ for $\dot{h} \approx 3\text{m/s}$, gaining about 16km/orbit at 200km, and \dot{h} decreasing slowly with gain in altitude.

3 Drag and Lift from Laboratory Data

Figure 1: Satellite surface element dA . Particle incident with momentum p_i at angle θ_i from surface normal \hat{n} scatters with outgoing momentum p_o . On smooth surfaces \hat{n}, p_i, p_o lie in the same plane.

going momentum p_o directed at outgoing angle θ_o with respect to \hat{n} . Momentum $p_r = p_o \cos(\theta_i + \theta_o)$ is the component of p_o reflected along the line of impact of p_i . When p_r opposes p_i the total momentum delivered is $p_i + p_r$ since the p_r recoils from dA ; in contrast, when p_r is in the same direction as p_i on the line of impact to p_i , the net momentum delivered is less than p_i , that is, $p_i - p_r$.

Figure 2: $f(\theta)$ vs. angle of incidence $\theta_i (= \theta)$ measured by the investigators cited.

This section reviews the momentum transfer method due to Boring and Humphris [8, 9], Knechtel and Pitts [10] and others (see[12]), with drag force examples including one making the case for aerodynamic lift.

The satellite is so massive compared to the air particles that particles bounce back unless its surfaces tilt away from the particle flux. Figure 1 shows a surface element of area dA as particles move toward it with satellite velocity \vec{V} , each carrying incident momentum p_i along the line of impact to bounce off with outgoing momentum p_o ; the surface normal \hat{n} serving as reference for both incident and outgoing angles θ_i and θ_o , respectively with θ_i and θ_o coplanar on smooth surfaces.

If $\theta_i = 0$ and $\theta_o = 0$, then $p_r = p_o$ and particles bounce back mostly into the line of impact and net momentum delivered to dA is $p_i + p_r$. If $\theta_i \neq 0$, p_o does not line up with \vec{V} and the net momentum may have a component that is perpendicular to \vec{V} . Net momentum along \vec{V} contributes to drag and the component perpendicular to \vec{V} may contribute to lift. In the following, Figure 1 describes the basis for the momentum transfer method [8, 9, 10, 11].

The particles may reflect elastically or inelastically with outgoing momentum p_o directed at outgoing angle θ_o with respect to \hat{n} . Momentum $p_r = p_o \cos(\theta_i + \theta_o)$ is the component of p_o reflected along the line of impact of p_i . When p_r opposes p_i the total momentum delivered is $p_i + p_r$ since the p_r recoils from dA ; in contrast, when p_r is in the same direction as p_i on the line of impact to p_i , the net momentum delivered is less than p_i , that is, $p_i - p_r$.

Thus, the total momentum delivered to dA may be written as $p_i + p_r = p_i(1 + f(\theta))$ where the function $f(\theta) = p_r/p_i$ and $\theta = \theta_i$. $f(\theta)$ is obtained from laboratory measurements of p_i and p_r and may be positive or negative[8, 9, 10, 11] as shown in Figure 2.

The utility of this approach is shown next as we review computations of drag coefficients of several examples in which the $f(\theta)$ is taken from experimental measurements of p_r and p_i plotted in Figure 2 that shows $f(\theta) > 0$ for $\theta_i < 30^\circ$ and $f(\theta) = 0$ between 30° and 60° to become negative at larger θ_i and falling to about -0.83 between 80° and 85° .

If area Σ represents the ram-facing area of the satellite (the area exposed to particle impacts), an arbitrary satellite shape will have dA 's pointing along their surface normals with θ depending on the position of dA on Σ , but for any dA with known pointing angle θ (measured from V), its projected area is $\cos\theta dA$. The number of impacts per unit time on projected area $\cos\theta dA$ is $dN/dt = n \times V \times dA \cos\theta$, and the elemental drag force on dA is

$$dF_D = p_i(1 + f(\theta))nVdA \cos\theta. \quad (8)$$

Substituting $p_i = mV$ and replacing m with the mean mass \bar{m} to account for multiple species in the air (e.g., AO and N₂), the mass density $\rho = \bar{m}n$, and the drag force may be computed from the surface integral

$$F_D = \rho V^2 \int_{\Sigma} (1 + f(\theta)) \cos \theta dA, \quad (9)$$

where ρ and V^2 have been taken outside the integral since they do not change over Σ in contrast to angle θ ; complex shapes may require numerical procedures to evaluate the integral in eq.9. The $f(\theta) = p_r/p_i$ used in that integral are obtained from laboratory measurements of ions or neutrals¹ but there are several shapes that are commonly used in satellites and some are discussed next.

The drag coefficient C_D may be obtained from eq.9 and from eq.2 that defines it. Comparing these two equations, an expression for C_D is

$$C_D = 2 \left(1 + \frac{1}{A_r} \int_{\Sigma} f(\theta) \cos \theta dA \right). \quad (10)$$

For example, the surface integral for a spherical satellite of radius r may be taken with V at the pole of spherical coordinates (r, θ, ϕ) with θ independent of ϕ resulting in surface area elements $dA = \pi r^2 \sin \theta d\theta$, and $A_r = \pi r^2$, making

$$C_D = 2 \left(1 + \int_0^{\pi/2} f(\theta) \cos \theta \sin \theta d\theta \right), \quad (11)$$

the term $\cos \theta \sin \theta$ giving maximum weight at $\theta = 45^\circ$. This illustrates why the drag coefficient for a diffusely reflecting sphere is a bit more than 2.0. For elastic specular reflections, one can show that $f(\theta) = \cos 2\theta$ making $C_D = 2(1 + 0) = 2.0$ exactly for the sphere.

Figure 3: Aerodynamic forces on the 3 satellite shapes (1), (2) and (3) to show the feasibility of lift. Details in text.

(1) Also for the sphere, the data of Knechtel and Pitts in Figure 2 show that $f(\theta)$ becomes negative around 30° ; making the integral in eq. 11 negative, to make $C_D < 2.0$ for the sphere.

The drag coefficient for a flat plate flying with surface normal inclined at angle θ to the velocity vector is

$$C_D = 2(1 + f(\theta)). \quad (12)$$

Such a simple result is also valid for the cone in terms of its half-angle, underlining the utility of $f(\theta)$; the following discusses the flat plate and the cone using the latter to point out how the asymmetry of a half-cone leads to an unbalance of outgoing momentum may lead to aerodynamic lift.

Figure 3 shows three satellites labeled (1), (2), and (3), respectively, each moving horizontally with velocity V that results in particle flux $F = nV$ impacting them from the left. The incident momentum per particle for each satellite is again $p_i = mV$ and p_o is the outgoing momentum. As in Figure 1, p_r is the component of p_o along the line of impact of p_i , and we introduce p_\perp the component of p_o perpendicular to the axes of satellites labeled (2) and (3).

Satellite (1) at the top of the figure is a flat plate flying head-on ($\theta = 0$) and the outgoing momentum p_o is equal to $p_r \leq p_i$,

¹Reference [12] reviews laboratory measurements with discussion of discrepancies with accommodation coefficients, competing processes in the atom-surface interaction, and the similarity between ion and neutral scattering from surfaces.

depending on surface properties. Its $C_D = 2(1 + f(0^\circ))$ where $f(0^\circ) \simeq 0.13$ to 0.26 from the laboratory data in Figure 2 to give $C_D \simeq 2.39 \pm 0.13$.

Satellite (2) is a cone of half-angle ϕ with drag coefficient $C_D = 2(1 + f(\pi/2 - \phi))$, valid for $\phi > 5$ to 10° depending on atmospheric temperature[12], with $f(\pi/2 - \phi)$ obtained from Figure 2 or similar data. The cone is impacted equally at all points on its surface, the diagram showing only two of the top and bottom impacts the outgoing momentum p_o (arrows with dashed lines) of reflected particles leaning toward the base with p_r in the same direction as p_i for net momentum $p_i - p_r$ and reduced drag in comparison with satellite (1).

The dotted vertical line connecting the ends of the two p_o arrows in satellite (2) is perpendicular to the cone axis lining up with p_\perp to symmetrically cancel momentum transfer perpendicular to the axis. For example, $\phi = 30^\circ$ corresponds to $\theta = 60^\circ$ for which $p_r/p_i < 0$ with value $f(\theta) \simeq -0.25$ from Figure 2. Thus $C_D = 2 \times 0.75 = 1.5$. A sharper cone with $\phi = 10^\circ$ has $C_D \simeq 2(1 - 0.83) = 0.34$ suggesting that C_D approaches 0 as $\phi \rightarrow 0$ according to the data of Figure 2. Of course, experience shows that the drag coefficient of a cone is less than that of the flat plate of object (1), and the sharper the cone the smaller the drag force and thereby C_D .

Figure 3's satellite (3) shows the cone of satellite (2) cut in half along its axis and flown as shown with its flat triangular face pointing up to the zenith so that only impacts from below contribute to drag while the outgoing p_o now has an unbalanced downward component p_\perp that would produce lift - in contrast to the balanced momenta reflected from the full cone of satellite (2) where all p_\perp cancel exactly.

4 Drag and Lift on a Tilted Flat Plate

Figure 4: Flat plate wing with chord c , thickness t and length l (into the paper), encounters air stream particles each with momentum $p_i = mV$ at angle of attack α_i on its lower plane that has area $c \times l$. Unit vector \hat{n} is the surface normal to define incident and outgoing angles θ_i and θ_o , respectively. Outgoing particles scatter at angle α_o such that $\alpha_i + \theta_i + \theta_o + \alpha_o = \pi$. The particle's net deflection is $\delta = \alpha_i + \alpha_o$ to allow decomposition of the outgoing momentum p_o into vertical $p_o \sin \delta$ and horizontal $p_o \cos \delta$ components.

is effectively a rectangular wing with surface area $A = c \times l$ and surface normal \hat{n} that gives the angle of incidence of p_i as $\theta_i = \pi/2 - \alpha_i$. Particles reflect into angular lobes with average outgoing momentum $p_o = mv_o$ exiting at $\theta_o = \pi/2 - \alpha_o$ with respect to \hat{n} , α_o being the direction of the centroid of the lobe of scattered particles, p_o measured from the wing's chord (width c). The net deflection from the incident

The unbalanced momentum of an asymmetric configuration is easily put into practice with a flat plate substituting $f(\theta)$ data into analytical expressions for C_D, C_L and L/D . Neutral and ion data apply[9] to characterize the scattering into lobes with maxima of angular widths that allow assignment of mean scattering angles, as in refs[17, 12].

Consider the flat plate in Fig. 4 moving horizontally to the left with velocity \vec{V} as shown and tilted at angle of attack α_i from \vec{V} to be struck by particles with incident momentum p_i . The plate has thickness t , width c , and length l (l not shown because it is perpendicular to the Figure). The plate

direction of p_i is then $\delta = \alpha_i + \alpha_o = \pi - (\theta_i + \theta_r)$. The small vector diagram (lower right) shows the horizontal and vertical components of the outgoing momentum, $p_o \cos \delta$ and $p_o \sin \delta$, respectively.

Angles, θ_m and θ_{ss} along the top are important in shielding objects on the top of the wing where they are drag-free, shielded from the particle flux. Particles have random thermal speeds that make their flux diverge from any point in space so that most lie within a cone of half-angle $\theta_m = a_m/V$ where $a_m = \sqrt{2k_B T/m}$ is the most probable speed of atomic mass m in a thermosphere with temperature T ($k_B =$ Boltzmann's constant). If $T = 0$, particles that skim the top edge of the wing would continue along the horizontal dashed line above the shaded region. When $T \neq 0$ particles invade the shaded region to get close to the back of the wing but only within θ_m . At low altitudes $T \approx 700K$ or less, and $\theta_m < 10^\circ$ even for higher temperatures around 1500K at higher altitudes. If $\alpha_i > \theta_m + \theta_{ss}$, angle θ_{ss} defines a self-shadowing region above the wing where there is no airstream and therefore no drag for instruments or other devices.

This rectangular plate is therefore a wing that may develop lift if momentum loss $\Delta p = p_i - p_o$ is less than some value that may be estimated with the experimental results of Xu et al.,[17] and the $f(\theta)$ data of Herrero and Cagiano[14, 12] (see Appendix for a discussion of the latter). The data of Xu et al.,[17] characterize inelastic scattering of 4.7 eV energy AO atoms on engineering surfaces that are used in satellites in low-earth-orbit. The four surfaces used were fluorinated ethylene propylene polymer (FEP), Aluminum (Al) - with a chromate conversion Alodine coating, solar cell cover glass (CG) with MgF2 coating, and glass-reinforced epoxy circuit board material (FR4). They give the average fractional energy loss $\Delta E/E_i$ for AO atoms scattered from smooth surfaces of FR4, Al, CG, and FEP as a function of deflection angle δ for incident angles θ_i of 60° , 45° , 30° , 15° , and 0° , the larger θ_i 's showing lobular scattering similar to previous observations at angles of attack as small as 5° [14, 12]. The angular distributions in those two data sets expand the range of angle of incidence θ_i to 85° - 0° , making it possible to assign mean scattering angles and energy distributions that yield fractional energy loss as a function of particle deflection δ .

Figure 5: Lift-to-drag ratio function $r(f_o, \delta)$, also denoted in the text as L/D , for four values of momentum ratio $f_o = p_o/p_i$. The solid horizontal line represents elastic scattering with $r(f_o, \delta) = 1.0$.

Drag is due to the net horizontal momentum $\Delta p_{hor} = p_i - p_o \cos \delta$ transferred to the wing chord c . Lift is strictly speaking due to the net \perp component of momentum transferred; it is vertical if the wing span l lies in the horizontal plane and therefore may be called lift, the perpendicular component being $\Delta p_{vert} = p_o \sin \delta$.

If dN/dt particles impact the wing chord per unit time, the drag force is $F_D = \Delta p_{hor} \times dN/dt$. Similarly, the lift force is $F_L = \Delta p_{vert} \times dN/dt$.

The projected area of the wing along \vec{V} is $A_c = lc \sin \alpha_i$ and $dN/dt = nVlc \sin \alpha_i$. Substituting $p_i = \bar{m}V$ and $\rho = \bar{m}n$, the drag force is

$$F_D = (1 - f_o \cos \delta) \rho V^2 A_c, \quad (13)$$

where $f_o = p_o/p_i$ and is not to be confused with p_r/p_i in $f(\theta) = p_r/p_i$. The projected area is $A_c = lc \sin \alpha_i$.

In the same way, the lift force is given by

$$F_L = f_o \sin \delta \rho V^2 A_c, \quad (14)$$

with drag coefficient $C_D = 2(1 - f_o \cos \delta)$ where this is identical to $C_D = 2(1 + f(\theta))$ in eq.12 with $f(\theta) = p_r/p_i$ and $p_r = -p_o \cos \delta$. The lift coefficient is $C_L = 2f_o \sin \delta$. Thus, the ratio of the forces is

equal to the ratio of the coefficients and may be called simply the L/D ratio, noting that it is precisely equal to the ratio function $r(f_o, \delta)$ of the two variables (f_o, δ) . So we write

$$\frac{L}{D} = \frac{F_L}{F_D} = \frac{C_L}{C_D} = r(f_o, \delta) = \frac{f_o \sin \delta}{1 - f_o \cos \delta}. \quad (15)$$

We reiterate that the outgoing momentum ratio $f_o = p_o/p_i \leq 1.0$ is a measure of momentum lost in the atom-surface interaction and can be obtained from the fractional energy loss $\Delta E/E_i$. $E_i = p_i^2/2m$ is the incident kinetic energy of particle with mass m , and $\Delta E = E_i - E_o = (p_i^2 - p_o^2)/2m$ is the energy loss itself. For perfectly elastic interactions, the change of momentum and energy are each zero and $f_o = 1.0$. For finite changes $\Delta p = p_i - p_o$ and known $p_o/p_i = f_o$ it follows that

$$f_o = \sqrt{1 - \frac{\Delta E}{E_i}}, \quad (16)$$

a relation to be applied below to obtain the lift-to-drag ratio L/D of eq.15 from the measurements of $\Delta E/E_i$ by Xu et al.[17] and Herrero and Cagiano[14]. For a given $f_o = p_o/p_i$ there will be a deviation angle δ_m of maximum L/D where $(\partial r/\partial \delta)_{f_o} = 0$ at $\delta_m = \cos^{-1}(f_o)$.

Figure 5 plots $r(f_o, \delta)$ against δ for $f_o = 1.0, 0.9, 0.8, 0.7$. For $f_o = 1.0$ the angle of maximum r occurs at $\delta = 0^\circ$ where r is infinite - shown by the solid black curve that monotonically decreases with δ to cross the horizontal line $r = 1.0$ at exactly 90° ; this corresponds exactly to 45° for the elastic case. The angles of maximum for the other three cases are (25.8° for $f_o=0.9$), (36.9° for $f_o=0.8$), and (45.6° for $f_o=0.7$) with respective magnitudes 2.06, 1.33, and 0.99 - all angles accessible in flight with the flat plate. When $r(f_o, \delta)$ exceeds 1.0 with $L/D > 1.0$, lift exceeds drag and the satellite climbs. The plots show that when $f_o = p_o/p_i < 0.7$ drag dominates for all angles δ (and all α_i) and the satellite cannot climb at all.

4.1 Specular elastic reflections

If the particles reflect specularly with no loss of energy, $p_o = p_i$, $f_o = 1$ and $\alpha_o = \alpha_i$ exactly, making the deviation $\delta = 2\alpha_i$ and $p_i - p_o \cos \delta = p_i(1 - \cos 2\alpha_i)$ to give

$$F_D = (1 - \cos 2\alpha_i)\rho V A_c. \quad (17)$$

Similarly, the lift force F_L becomes

$$F_L = \sin 2\alpha_i \rho V A_c, \quad (18)$$

and the lift-to-drag ratio is

$$\frac{L}{D} = \frac{F_L}{F_D} = \frac{\sin 2\alpha_i}{(1 - \cos 2\alpha_i)}. \quad (19)$$

Figure 5 shows L/D vs δ from 20° to 100° with the solid black line ($f_o = 1.0$) crossing the y-axis at exactly 90° with $C_L/C_D = 1.0$, corresponding to $\alpha_i = 45^\circ$ for the ideal case of elastic scattering.

4.2 Quasi-specular inelastic reflections

Equations 15 and 16 make it possible to include the effect of inelastic impacts to obtain the variation of $r(f_o, \delta)$ (equivalently L/D) with deviation δ from 20° to 100° ; using the elastic scattering result $\delta = 2\alpha_i$ as a rough guide, this range would cover angles of attack α_i from about 10° to 50° . The lower limit of 10° is the minimum angle of attack that provides sufficient shielding of objects atop the wing. The upper limit of 50° is where the energy loss is likely to be large with $f_o < 0.7$ (see Figure 5).

Figure 6(a) shows the fractional energy loss $\Delta E/E_i$ plotted against the deviation angle δ , the data points at 40° , 60° , 80° , and 100° taken from Xu et al.[17]; Applying eq.16 to the $\Delta E/E_i$'s of Figure 6(a) gives

Figure 6: (a) Variation of $\Delta E/E_i$ with deflection angle δ and (b) Variation of $f_o = p_o/p_i$ with δ . Four sets of data with discrete points taken from Xu et al.[17] for the surfaces FR4, Al, CG, and FEP as listed in the text.

the variation of the outgoing momentum ratio $f_o = p_o/p_i$ with δ on the right in Figure 6(b). to be applied directly to eq.15 for the L/D ratio of as a function of δ .

However, we require the variation of L/D down to $\delta \approx 20^\circ$; for this, Figure 8 of Xu et al.[17] shows that the variation of $\Delta E/E_i$ is essentially linear over the δ range 40° to 100° as reproduced in the data points of Figure 6(a). The older data that supported NASA's GRM[12] discussed in the Appendix gave $f(\theta)$ for $\theta = 85^\circ$, corresponding to angle of attack $\alpha_i = 5^\circ$, and peak angles of the scattering lobes at $\delta \simeq 19^\circ$ indicating sub-specular scattering with $\delta \approx 24^\circ$, not expected to follow the $\delta = 2\alpha_i$ elastic scattering rule, giving the measured angle of attack $\alpha_i = 5^\circ$.

Figure 7: Variation of L/D over extended deflection angles δ from 20° to 100° .

it encounters. AO exposure is less if descent occurs at angles of attack near zero. Happily, very low angle of attack exposes any devices on the top of the wing to the air stream to perhaps develop the necessary drag to achieve descent. The data in Figure 7 may be used at this point to illustrate implementation of descent at low-angles of attack in a more complete picture of the flat plate wing.

Figures 8(a) and 8(b) illustrate the situation. Particles that graze the upper edge of the wing in Fig.8a

Thus, the $\Delta E/E_i$'s of Figure 6(a) convert to $f_o = \sqrt{1 - \Delta E/E_i}$ per eq.16 to obtain the variation of f_o with δ (Figure 6(b)) that, applied to eq.15, yield the variation of the ratio function $r(f_o, \delta) = L/D$, the dimensionless lift-to-drag ratio, shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 shows that lift dominates over drag ($L/D > 1.0$) for deflection angles from 20° to about 65° , dropping to less than 1.0 ($L/D < 1.0$) above 65° , and then decreases to nearly 0.5 at 100° . This means that the satellite, in the form of the flat plate, can climb with angles of attack roughly between 10° and 30° , fly level at roughly 30° ($\delta = 60^\circ$), and descend at angles of attack greater than 30° . The L/D ratio at angle of attack 20° ($\delta = 40^\circ$) favors climb at 1.5 to 2.0.

The flat plate descent at high angles of attack α_i of 30° to 50° exposes the lift-producing side of the flat plate to air particles, particularly to AO which degrades the surfaces

would all move past it along the horizontal dashed line were it not for their random thermal speeds (detail in description of Fig.4) that lets them approach downwards by angle $\theta_m = (\sqrt{2k_bT/m})/V$, most particles falling within angle θ_m from the horizontal and gradually decreasing in number to become negligible at θ_m - the decrease shown by the green color shade in the angular region of θ_m . This shows that self-shading begins at θ_m measured from the horizontal, with complete shielding in the region covered by θ_{ss} (shown here only for the top edge of the wing). This region is controlled by the angle of attack α_i since $\theta_{ss} = \alpha_i - \theta_m$.

Figure 8: (a) Flat plate wing moving to the left with the airstream striking its chord from the left with velocity \vec{V} at angle of attack α_i . (b) Variation of L/D with angle of attack α_i for the Al surface, the lowest lift-producing surface from Fig.7 of the four surfaces FR4, Al, CG, and FEP reported by Xu et al.[17]t.

A shield plate SP placed in this region protects equipment (blue boxes) from the particle flux; SP being a durable obstacle whose surface if it degrades affects only the range of α_i where drag transitions from zero to a value that leads to the desired rate of descent. A ram sensor would indicate the angle of attack and would check lift vs. descent against flight altitude data. Especially useful as the SP degrades and changes the α_i range for descent. Since θ_m is roughly 10° for thermospheric temperatures in LEO, the shielding angle may be estimated from $\theta_{ss} = \alpha_i - 10^\circ$. With device height likely to be less than 3cm, SP 's distance from the leading edge is $3 \times \cos \theta_{ss} = .2.9\text{cm}$ for $\alpha_i = 25^\circ$; in harmony with a practical wing chord $c = 100\text{cm}$.

Adding a straight line from 0° to 10° in Figure 8b illustrates the region where drag would dominate to implement descending flight - as approximate as it is, it still illustrates that there will be a region with α_i falling from 10° to about 5° where lift decreases rapidly. The region in α_i less than about 5° where descent becomes effective. Of course these numbers may be specified more closely with additional modeling.

The discontinuous jump in the slope of the L/D curve indicates that L/D changes rapidly with α_i the illustration suggesting that perhaps the range in angle of attack to transition from climb to descent may be very narrow and difficult to reproduce in flight. This accentuates the need for a sensitive ram sensor to keep tight control of the angle of attack with its signal fed to control attitude using, e.g., control surfaces, momentum wheels, or other, in all three phases of flight.

These and other issues may be addressed with simulations based on eq.15 when designing a flight prototype of the flat plate satellite. This description laying out the approach to fly a flat plate with shield plate at its top to enable lift at angles of attack roughly 20° and lower to begin descent at lower angles of attack with level flight somewhere in between.

5 Discussion

Applications of satellites orbiting without propulsion at altitudes as low as 150 km are likely to be many; the notion that the flat plate wing can climb, fly level, and descend without propulsion is revolutionary, especially with the prospect of maneuvering to change position horizontally as well as vertically. Climbing rate is directly proportional to wing area and air density, decreasing with altitude. In the area of orbital debris it could, for example, climb to say 400km to attach to another satellite and bring it down to detach at 150km for rapid re-entry providing active removal of orbital debris with a reusable vehicle.

Satellite Surfaces in-orbit will likely degrade due to AO erosion that removes material from the wing surface. AO erosion E , measured in cm of thickness lost from exposure to AO, is the main cause of satellite surface degradation in LEO. $E = F \times Y$ where the AO fluence $F = n_O \times V_{Sat} \times t_{exp}$ is in [atoms/cm²] and the erosion yield Y is in [cm³/atom]. At 200 km $n_O \simeq 10^{10}/\text{cm}^3$, $V_{Sat} = 8 \times 10^5 \text{cm/s}$, and with exposure time t_{exp} of a year, the fluence F is $2.6 \times 10^{23} \text{atoms/cm}^2$. The yield Y varies from $10^{-24} \text{cm}^3/\text{atom}$ for polyimide Kapton and other polymers used in space to about $10^{-27} \text{cm}^3/\text{atom}$ for metals like Titanium, Tungsten and others with erosion E going from about 0.2cm for polymers to 10^{-4}cm for metals.[26, 27, 28], strongly favoring a metal-coated wing surface. The bombardment of the lower surface of the wing by high velocity AO and N₂ does not necessarily destroy the L/D function; the impacts may erode it but not destroy the momentum transfer kinematics required, and this can only be assessed in orbit.

Maneuvering to avoid collisions with other satellites. Since the lift force is perpendicular to the wing span, rolling the wing directs the lift at some angle to the vertical to accelerate the wing horizontally as well as vertically; by exactly how much must await actual flight tests but will benefit from detailed modeling using the scheme developed here. This approach to collision avoidance would require prediction of positions of other satellites in a time scale of perhaps hours or days. However, it is a direct approach compared to the present approach under development that requires multiple satellites collecting data to send to ground-based computers, (e.g., NOAA's SWPC) to predict position and time of neutral density enhancements that then would be used to change satellite trajectories, also requiring predictions of positions of other satellites.

Space communications at 150 to 200km without propulsion power - allowing solar panel power to be used mostly in receiver/transmitter RX/TX functions. Satellite lifetime would be limited by AO erosion to one or more years. Power reduction to receive/transmit by more than 10X - for example, operating at 150km instead of 600km - 1/4th the distance for 1/16 the RX/TX power.

Laboratory Experiments should continue to compare laboratory results with flight performance and thereby obtain a basis to enhance the design process. The present data sets are sufficient for what may be called a preliminary design to be tested in flight to further elucidate the validity of the simple result obtained for the flat plate.

Attitude control in pitch, roll, and yaw with small thrusters, control surfaces, or momentum wheels stabilize the wing attitude. Much along these lines has been learned in the CubeSat generation. Control to adjust angle of attack (pitch) requires a ram sensor of which there are actual devices available, their signals available to monitor roll and yaw with additional sensors (star cameras, horizon sensors,...).

6 Conclusions

This paper derived analytical expressions for the drag and lift forces on a flat plate satellite; the expressions use laboratory measurements of atomic oxygen impacts on some satellite surfaces to give the lift-to-drag ratio L/D as a function of the satellite attitude - its angle of attack - with energy loss known from the laboratory data. It uses the momentum transfer ratio function $f(\theta) = p_r/p_i$ of Boring and Humphris and others[8, 9, 10, 11] where p_i is the momentum of the incident particle and $p_r = p_o \cos(\theta_i + \theta_o)$ is the component of outgoing momentum p_o that lines up with the line of impact of p_i ; the net deflection angle

of p_o from the original direction of p_i is $\delta = \pi - (\theta_i + \theta_o)$. The lift to drag ratio L/D is a function of two variables given in eq.15 as

$$L/D = r(f_o, \delta) = \frac{f_o \sin \delta}{1 - f_o \cos \delta}$$

where the variable $f_o = p_o/p_i$ depends on δ . To operate the flat plate satellite, knowledge of the L/D ratio as a function of angle of attack α_i is desirable and this follows from $\alpha_i = \pi/2 - \theta_i$. Laboratory data gave the variation of f_o with δ in terms of the measured fractional energy loss $\Delta E/E_i$ using $f_o = (1 - \Delta E/E_i)^{1/2}$ to obtain the variation of L/D with deviation δ first and then relate it to the angle of attack $\alpha_i = \pi/2 - \theta_i$. The fractional energy loss $\Delta E/E_i$ has been measured by Xu et al.[17] for 4.7 eV AO impacting 4 different surfaces - an indispensable data set for this work that covers δ from 40° to 130° ; in those measurements the angle of incidence θ_i ranged from 0° to 60° , showing $\Delta E/E_i$ decreasing monotonically with θ_i from about 0.8 at $\theta_i = 0^\circ$ and between 0.2 and 0.3 at $\theta_i = 60^\circ$ depending on the surface material - the energetics consistent with atom-surface interaction knowledge. This work requires values of f_o at $\delta \approx 20^\circ$ that is, $\theta_i < 10^\circ$, and these were obtained from older data at $\theta_i = 85^\circ$ [12, 14] with 9 eV N_2^+ impacts on smooth Mo surfaces.

The results show the possibility of a satellite in the shape of a flat rectangular wing flying in Very Low earth Orbit (VLEO) without propulsion from 150km and up and with the ability to climb, descend, or maintain constant altitude controlled by adjustment of the angle of attack - the lowest altitude as allowed by impact heating. An object in orbit around earth constantly falls toward the center of the earth, bound to it with negative total energy to remain in orbit with its large tangential velocity. Drag opposes the tangential velocity to dissipate satellite energy and increase its rate of fall with a negative radial velocity. Lift deflects the air particles downwards to impart upward momentum to the satellite with positive radial velocity that decreases its rate of fall as the satellite continues to falling and its total energy remaining negative.

As Newton noted regarding the Moon's orbit around the earth, a satellite constantly falls towards the center of the earth. With lift it falls less rapidly, with drag more rapidly, and when lift equals drag, it falls like the Moon keeping its altitude constant.

APPENDIX

In Figure 2 the two data points at $\theta = 80^\circ$ and 85° were obtained by Herrero and Cagiano [13, 14] in support of NASA's Geopotential Research Mission (GRM). GRM's goal to provide sensitive measurements of earth's geoid used two long cylindrical spacecraft flying at 200 km[15]. Impacts with the lateral surface of a long cylinder were expected to significantly increase drag[13] and measurements of $f(\theta)$ were required for quantitative drag estimates due to grazing particle impacts on the lateral surface - requiring angles of incidence above and below $\approx 80^\circ$. This led to laboratory measurements of particle scattering from surfaces with capability to reach extreme scattering angles of $\theta_i = 85^\circ$ as in references[14, 12]. Those data showed quasi-specular scattering of N_2^+ ions from smooth Molybdenum surfaces providing $f(\theta)$ at θ 80° and 85° . N_2^+ was convenient to use over the preferred neutral N_2 since previous results indicated that ion impacts blend smoothly with neutral impacts at energies below 20 eV - discussed further in the Appendix.

The GRM data[12, 14] measured N_2^+ scattering from smooth Molybdenum (Mo) surfaces at energies from 1 to 40 eV and angles of incidence θ_i from 30° to 85° . The N_2^+ reflected into relatively narrow lobes as measured in a rotatable spherical condenser energy analyzer[14].

The difference between ion and neutral scattering is negligible according to Boring and Humphris[9] who before 1973 measured the momentum transfer function $f(\theta)$ by N_2 impact on surface samples of the Echo satellites at energies 10 eV and up. For atomic oxygen O, intensity around 5 eV was too small to produce

detectable $f(\theta)$ in the experiment but reliable at 20 eV and up. They also measured $f(\theta)$ in O^+ and N_2^+ impacts from 4 eV and up, and found that the energy variation of $f(\theta)$ of N_2 and of AO blended smoothly with the O^+ and N_2^+ variation at 20 eV. This led them to suggest that the difference between neutral and ion momentum transfer is negligible, and that O^+ ion impact data taken between 4 and 20 eV energy could be used to compute the drag coefficients corresponding to the neutral atomic oxygen O. We assume that for N_2^+ scattering here.

Figure A.1: Details are given in the text.

Figure A.1 shows the angular distributions for two energies 8 and 15 eV at angle of incidence $\theta_i = 85^\circ$ adapted from reference[12]. The reflected ions are confined to relatively narrow lobes peaking at 70° ($\alpha_o = 20^\circ$) for 8 eV and about 78° ($\alpha_o = 12^\circ$) for 15 eV; both reflection lobes being sub-specular with net deflections larger than for the specular case. For these data, only the value $f(\theta = 85^\circ) = -0.83$ was published and shown in Fig. 2; the distribution and α_o required is the one at 9 eV kinetic energy and that can be obtained from the data in the figure.

Figure A.1 also shows the momenta in red: p_i on the left, and on the right p_r and the p_o 's separately for each energy with their respective outgoing angles α_o . As defined above, $f(\theta) = p_r/p_i$ with p_r being the component of p_o along the line of p_i , or $p_r = p_o \cos \delta$. Therefore $f(\theta) = (p_o/p_i) \cos \delta$ defines the variable

$$f_o = (p_o/p_i) = |f(\theta)| / \cos \delta. \quad (20)$$

Since the proper kinetic energy for N_2 is 9 eV, the proper value of δ is closer to the angle at 8 eV than to the one at 15 eV. Energy changing from 8 to 15 eV ($\Delta E = 7eV$) decrease the angle from 20° to about 12° ($\Delta\alpha = 8^\circ$) and $\alpha_o \simeq 19^\circ$ at 9 eV.

With $\cos 19^\circ \simeq 0.95$ and $f(\theta) = -0.83$, eq.20 gives $f_o \simeq 0.88$ at $\delta = 19^\circ$ in concurrence with the extrapolation of points in Fig 6b and corresponds to $\Delta E/E_i \simeq 0.23$ per eq.16.

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